

➤ Preprint fact checking

Scoop protection

Preprints allow you to establish priority for your discoveries. 99.3% of preprint authors reported no scoop problems.¹

Preprints are journal compatible

Over 1,200 journals operate policies compatible with preprints.²

Preprints are good quality

Two thirds of bioRxiv preprints appear in a journal within two years.³
Quality of reporting is within a similar range as that of peer-reviewed articles.⁴

Smoother path to publication

Many journals allow preprint transfers directly from servers.¹ Some editors scout preprints and invite submissions to their journal.

Infographics by ASAPbio Fellows:

Ana Dorrego-Rivas (@adorrego_r), Carrie Iwema
and Mafalda Pimentel (@Maf_Pimentel)

➤ ASAPbio

Find more information at ASAPbio.org

Sources:

1. Sever *et al.* bioRxiv 833400; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/833400>
2. Sherpa Romeo: <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>
3. Abdill and Blehman. *eLife* 2019;8:e45133
doi: [10.7554/eLife.45133](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.45133)

4. Carneiro, C.F.D. *et al.* Comparing quality of reporting between preprints and peer-reviewed articles in the biomedical literature. *Res Integr Peer Rev* 5, 16 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-020-00101-3>

CC BY 4.0

